

Determination of Assessment Live Load For Short-Span Bridges

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ABSTRACT:

A key component of bridge structural assessment is the formulation of an appropriate assessment live load for the bridge evaluation. Values for assessment live load from codes can produce overly conservative effects hence the need for the application of site-specific assessment live load. This research employs the application of basic statistical analysis on traffic count data to determine a bridge assessment live load using the Benin-Sagamu Overpass bridge as a case study. Inspection of the vehicular movements on the bridge was carried out to estimate the traffic composition while there was also the performance of traffic count under five different vehicle weight classes. The results from the statistical analysis of the traffic count data were modified with factors that defined the traffic composition of the bridge in order to produce a site-specific assessment live load model. The statistical analysis produced a mean vehicle assessment live load of 29.2T (286.4KN) and a characteristic load of 46T (451KN). The mean vehicle assessment live load was enhanced with bridge traffic composition factors adopted from CS 454 to derive the assessment vehicular load in this study. The axle weights and equivalent distances of the live load vehicle were also adopted from CS 454. The bridge can thus be analysed with the derived vehicular load and its durability determined.

Keywords: Bridge assessment live load, bridge assessment vehicle, site-specific assessment live load.

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INTRODUCTION

The derivation of a site-specific assessment live load model for a given bridge is very important in evaluating bridge conditions and optimising cost-effective bridge maintenance schedules [1a]. The general assessment live load models in codes can produce conservative results because these loads were meant to be applied to a large range of bridge types and spans under the most aggressive traffic [1a]. Therefore, assessment live load models in codes may not be specifically valid for a particular bridge condition assessment, leading to unnecessary maintenance works (in the case when live loads are too conservative) or sudden catastrophic disaster (in the case of underestimation of live loads) [1a].

The application of bridge design live load from codes in bridge durability assessment does not represent the current bridge condition realities. The possibility of the bridge experiencing such extreme traffic live load used to predict the bridge behaviour is usually kept minimal during design. It is expected that the bridge during its lifespan never gets to experience the design traffic live loads

[1b]. Therefore, for an accurate bridge condition assessment, the development of a site-specific live load model is vital.

The development of a live load model that would represent traffic on a bridge is one of the most challenging aspects of bridge reliability analysis since there are large variabilities inherent in vehicle-induced loads [2]. The modelling of the traffic load on a bridge involves more than specifying the vehicle weight and includes many factors such as Gross Vehicle Weight (GVW), number of axles and their spacing, distribution of GVW on the axles, multiple vehicle presence, transverse position of vehicles, and characteristics of dynamic effects of the live loads [2]. All of these constitute the vehicular traffic and assessment live load composition that is specific to that particular bridge.

The ability to obtain accurate information regarding the vehicular traffic composition and assessment live load composition hinges on the availability of a structural health monitoring (SHM) system which may include equipment such as Weigh-In-Motion sensors. When these are not available, there may be some level of difficulty as to how else an assessment live load can be derived. This research employs the use of manual traffic count data to estimate a site-specific assessment live load model modified with traffic composition factors obtained from [3].

As recommended by [3], actions or loads to be assessed during bridge structural durability assessment are to be defined using representative models. Actions or loads to be assessed may include all or some of the following loads: dead and superimposed dead load, carriageway traffic loading (live load), accidental vehicle loading, footway loading, wind loading, thermal loading and longitudinal traffic loading. [3] further recommends that the characteristic actions for dead load and superimposed dead loads shall be derived from the geometry of the structure and the unit weights of materials while those for traffic live loading shall be defined for the assessment using an assessment live loading (ALL) model that represents the level of traffic to be assessed, the influence of the road surface category on the impact effects of vehicles and the influence of the traffic flow category on the likelihood of vehicle overloading and lateral bunching. Assessment live loads (just as design live loads) are generally represented in the form of a design truck [2] or a combination of uniformly distributed load (UDL) and knife edge loads or just UDL.

[4] adopted the use of statistical analysis on bridge-specific measurements to derive a representative live load model such that the resulting live load model integrates site-specific conditions such as traffic volume, bridge natural frequency and damping, road alignment, vehicle suspension, speed environment, traffic mix, proximity to heavy industry, traffic barrier design. The site-specific conditions were obtained from data given by SHM systems installed on the bridge over a given period. Coupled with the SHM system, observations from CCTV cameras installed on the bridge provided extra information on the traffic composition of the bridge.

[5] also reiterated that the prediction of loads and uncertainties over long periods requires the use of statistics and reliability concepts. The reliability theory quantifies the uncertainty associated with the development of a site-specific assessment load model at the serviceability and ultimate limit states while statistical methods are used to process vehicle data records collected from WIM stations and analysed to draw conclusions and make decisions regarding the site-specific assessment load model.

[3] specifies assessment live load models for vehicles up to 44 tonnes and these models incorporate site-specific conditions on road surface characteristics and traffic volume. [6] specifies that the assessment live load is the ultimate load which occurs with a return period of 200,000 years or has a 0.06% chance of being exceeded in 120 years [4]. This characteristic load can produce overly conservative results.

This research aimed at estimating the assessment live load by applying basic statistical analysis traffic count data estimated for 120 years. Other data such as site-specific traffic composition, traffic volume, and road surface category, were estimated by observation and values adopted from [3]. The Benin Sagamu Bypass overhead twin bridge has been used to demonstrate the research concept.

Figure 1. View of the Benin-Sagamu Bypass overhead bridge

METHODS

The methods applied in this research involve estimation of the Annual Average Daily Traffic (AADT) from traffic count and estimating the total number of vehicles for 120 years which will ply the road. From the statistical data, the mean vehicle load and the characteristic vehicle load were determined.

Manual Traffic Count

A traffic survey was carried out for five days. The vehicles were classified into five categories according to GVW given in [7] as shown in Table 1. The Eurocode used traffic data for fourteen days to derive design live load models [5] and generally effective traffic surveys may need to take at least seven days. However, due to the complexities and challenges faced during the period of the traffic survey, only 5-day traffic data have been used to illustrate the research concept.

Annual Average Daily Traffic

The information from the traffic survey helps in the determination of AADT for each category of vehicle. This is necessary as it aids in estimating the number of vehicles in a certain weight class that have used the bridge for whatever number of years, in this case, 120 years.

AADT was estimated for each category of vehicle by taking the average of the 12-hour traffic count for each category. This in itself may not be enough to justify the AADT but this approach has been adopted for illustrative purposes.

The total number of categorised vehicles was calculated and then simulated with the traffic model formula of equation 1 [8].

$$T = 365 \times AADT [(1 + r)^n - 1]/(r) \quad (1)$$

Where T is the cumulative number of vehicles, n is the total number of years considered (120 years for this research) and r is the annual growth rate adopted from [10].

Gross Vehicle Weight

In the absence of in-situ measurement of vehicle weights or axle weights from WIM sensors, the vehicle classes needed an estimation of GVW. The weights used in this study were adopted from [7] according to the vehicle classes available and are shown in Table 1. For this study, the various vehicle classes have been represented as follows; CA for Cars, BU for Buses, LO for Lorries, TR for Trucks and LT for Large Trucks.

Table 1. Approximate Vehicle Weights for Classes of Vehicles

VEHICLE TYPES	CA	BU	LO	TR	LT
TONNAGE (T)	2	20	31	46	51

The GVW from Table 1 is multiplied by each entry of a vehicle and statistically analysed to find the mean vehicle load. The mean vehicle load represented the assessment live load which was later modified by site-specific factors.

Assessment Live Load Models

[3] recommends that for assessment purposes, the characteristic traffic actions for normal or restricted traffic should be represented using either Assessment Live Load Model 1 (ALL model 1) or Assessment Live Load Model 2 (ALL model 2). For short-span bridges typically below 20m, the code adopts ALL model 1 and this has been employed in this study.

Modification Factors

The final live load specific to the bridge which was adopted needed further modification factors to make it site-specific. These modification factors ensure the assessment live load is not overestimated nor underestimated. These factors have been discussed as follows:

1. Impact Factor

The impact factor is determined by the category of road surface on the bridge and it is multiplied by the most critical axle of the assessment load. The impact factors recommended in table 5.9a of [3] have been used in this work. [3] further gave certain conditions to determine the quality of a particular road surface using the traffic speed condition survey (TRACS) or by observation of Heavy Goods Vehicle (HGV) over the structure. When the observation of vehicles is used, [3] gave seven (7) criteria to determine if a bridge road surface is poor and they are:

1. Subsidence, dip in the road or poor profile run-on slab;
2. The bridge is in a dip;
3. The vehicle bounces in such a manner that the driver or passengers are aware of significant alterations in their seat pressure whilst on any part of the bridge or run-on slab;
4. Sub-base deterioration;
5. The vehicle pitches locally due to a change in the short wavelength vertical road profile on the bridge;
6. Any obvious visually extensive or severe deterioration to the surface, such as potholing;
7. Any noticeable steps in expansion joints on the bridge that are felt as well as heard by the driver.

If none of the aforementioned conditions are met, then the bridge road surface category can pass as 'good'.

When considering the third and seventh factors highlighted, this illustrative example would pass as 'poor' in the road surface category. An image has been shown of expansion joints on the bridge deck which determined the road surface to be poor, in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Road Surface at the Bridge's Expansion Joint

2. Traffic Flow Factor

More site-specific data is applied to the assessment live load model in the form of the traffic flow. This can be high, medium and low [3]. Depending on the category, the factor is multiplied appropriately to the assessment live load.

Firstly, the traffic flow category is determined from Table 5.5N3 of [3]. To determine this, the Annual Average Hourly Heavy Goods Vehicle Flow (AAHG VF) is determined from equation 2.

$$AAHG VF = \frac{\text{Total annual 2-way HGV flow}}{8760} \quad (2)$$

After determining if the flow category is high, medium or low, the appropriate flow factor is picked from Table 5.9b of [3].

3. Dynamic Amplification Factors (DAF)

This takes into account the dynamic effects of transient vehicles on the bridge. The dynamic characteristics of vehicles on bridges have been modelled by several researchers but the Assessment and Rehabilitation of Central European Highway Structures (ARCHES) Report recommendations have been adopted in this work [9]. The ARCHES report showed lower values of DAF than those recommended by the Eurocodes. The recommended DAF for ISO class A road (Main Road) within the span of 25m is 1.15 and this was adopted for this research.

RESULTS

Traffic Data Composition

Traffic results indicate that 62.3% of the total data collected involved small cars having an approximate weight of 2T. Even if these cars were overloaded, they may have a limited effect on the structural performance of the bridge. However, research has shown that vehicles with lower axle weights are known to have caused the most severe effects on bridges [3]. That is to say, no matter the weight of the vehicle, it is important to consider all vehicle weight types for structural durability purposes. The percentage of each category of vehicle captured in the study is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Percentage of Vehicle Classes

Annual Average Daily Traffic

The results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Annual Average Daily Traffic from the Survey

VEHICLE TYPES	CA	BU	LO	TR	LT
AADT	13,775	5,739	315	1,202	1,068

The total number of various vehicle categories is then calculated and simulated with the traffic model formula of equation 1. Taking n as 120 years, with an annual growth rate of 4% [10], the cumulative number of vehicles is shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Cumulative Number of Vehicles for 120 Years

VEHICLE TYPES	CA (Nos)	BU (Nos)	LO (Nos)	TR (Nos)	LT (Nos)
No. of vehicles for 120 years (Lognormal Distribution)	13,784,241,198	5,742,850,108	315,211,323	1,205,808,395	1,068,716,486
Total for all vehicle types	22,116,827,510				

From the total number of vehicles for each vehicle class projected for 120 years (the number of years most bridges are designed for), the mean vehicle weight which would ply the bridge route was used as the basis for the live load model.

Traffic data naturally represents a lognormal distribution; therefore, the data was converted to a normal distribution by taking the natural logarithm (\ln) of the cumulative number of vehicles. This will change the data from lognormal data to normally distributed data. The results are shown in table 4.

Table 4. Cumulative Number of Vehicles for 120 Years in Normal Distribution

VEHICLE TYPES	CA (Nos)	BU (Nos)	LO (Nos)	TR (Nos)	LT (Nos)
No. of vehicles for 120 years (Normal Distribution)	23.35	22.47	19.57	20.91	20.79
Total for all vehicle types	107.09				

To ensure the assessment live load is site-specific, the GVW of each vehicle was multiplied by each vehicle class in Table 4 above. The GVW were taken from [7] and are as shown in Table 1. These vehicle weights are multiplied by the numbers in Table 1 to give Table 5 which expresses these data in terms of mean vehicle weight.

Table 5. Vehicular Counts and Their Weights (Normal Distribution)

VEHICLE TYPES	CA	BU	LO	TR	LT
Tonnage (T)	46.70	449.4	606.67	961.86	1,060.29
Mean Vehicle Weight	29.2				

This mean vehicle weight representing the vehicle model was compared to the closest vehicle model in [3]. After picking the vehicle model, the axle loads and dimensions of the vehicle represent the assessment live load of the bridge.

Characteristic Load

Another method of determining the assessment live load is by deducing the characteristic vehicle load from the traffic data using the natural lognormal distribution obtained from the site. Table 6 shows the characteristic vehicle load of 46T for the case study.

Table 6. Cumulative Number of Vehicles for 120 Years

VEHICLE TYPES	CA (Nos)	BU (Nos)	LO (Nos)	TR (Nos)	LT (Nos)
No. of vehicles for 120 years (Lognormal Distribution)	13,784,241,198	5,742,850,108	315,211,323	1,205,808,395	1,068,716,486
Total Vehicles	22,116,827,510				
Mean	11.85T				
Standard Deviation	17.17T				
Characteristic Load	$11.85 + 1.96(17.17) = 46T$				

Vehicle Assessment Live Load

From the study, the mean vehicle assessment live load which pertains to the bridge is 29.2T while the characteristic vehicle load is 46T. The final assessment live load to be adopted can be determined by that which gives the most consequential effect during the bridge live load analysis. Studies have shown that vehicles with lower GVW can have more devastating effects compared to vehicles with higher GVW [3]. This is because the vehicles which project more dynamic effects on the bridge are those with lower GVW.

For this study, the mean vehicle assessment load is used to illustrate the research concept. This load is nearest to Vehicle Assessment Load Model A of Table B.1 of [3]. The vehicle model classes and axle weights of [3] are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Diagram Showing Vehicular Loads

Modification of Axle Loads

From Table 5.9a of [3], 1.8 is taken as the impact factor since the road surface has already been classed as poor. This factor is multiplied by the most critical axle load which in this case is 113KN load. This gives the most critical axle load as 203.4KN.

Also, using the data from the traffic count, the total annual 2-way HGV flow is 91,911,619.

Therefore, from equation 2, we have;

$$AAHGVF = \frac{91911619}{8760} = 10,492$$

This value is greater than 70. From table 5.5N3 of [3], this corresponds to the high traffic flow category. From table 5.9b of [3] the traffic flow factor is 1.0, hence.

The DAF of 1.15 has been multiplied by the assessment vehicle loads to give the final axle weights as shown in Table 7. A line diagram showing the modified axle loads is illustrated in Figure 5.

Table 7. Modified Axle Weights and Distances

Axle weight (KN)		Distance (m)	
W_1	73.6	$O_1 = O_2$	1
W_2	73.6	A_1	1.2
W_3	233.9	A_2	3.9
W_4	85.1	A_3	1

Figure 5. Diagram of Modified Axle Loads

This modified axle load can be effectively used for analysis to determine the bridge's current structural condition using any method applicable.

DISCUSSION

From research, it has been proven that the maximum vehicle axle load does not necessarily produce the most adverse effects [3]. The traffic statistics used to derive the design live loads of Eurocode didn't show the heaviest axle loads but it showed the highest frequency of heavy axle loads [5]. Furthermore, it was also established that vehicles with heavier axle loads do not produce as much dynamic effects compared to vehicles with lesser axle loads [9]. This emphasises the fact that just taking the dynamic effects and resulting shear and maximum moment effects from the vehicle with the largest gross vehicle weight or axle load will not effectively predict the most severe danger on the bridge. This study therefore proposed an alternative assessment live load model which will most likely show the most severe load effect.

CONCLUSION

A means by which site-specific assessment live load of a bridge, formulated using data from traffic counts have been demonstrated in this research. Although there were no means to measure all the traffic composition needed for a more detailed analysis, [3] provided ways to estimate some information about traffic composition by observation of the bridge and vehicular movements on it, thus making the assessment live load site-specific. These with the application of statistical methods enabled the determination of the assessment live load.

The methods proffered by this research can be used in bridge durability assessment as was shown in a previous study by the authors [11]. The assessment live load from this work is not far-fetched from the typical design axle load from Eurocode which is 300KN. This shows from the traffic studies that the effect of live actions on the bridge may not have exceeded design loads just yet and is operating within design constraints despite the increase in traffic.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

No conflict of interest.

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